

Implementation of Science and ICT Education and Access for Marginalized Communities in Government Schools of Sarlahi, Nepal

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Abstract

This study assessed the implementation status of science and ICT education in government secondary schools of Sarlahi District in Madhesh Pradesh, alongside the accessibility of these schools for marginalized groups, particularly OBC and Muslim children. Utilizing a descriptive-cum-exploratory research design, quantitative data were gathered via simple random sampling of secondary students using structured interviews, complemented by purposive sampling for qualitative in-depth interviews with school administrators. Results indicated that although 92.4 percent of students reported science teacher availability, staffing shortages persist in some schools. Only 29.7 percent rated science laboratories as good, with 30.3 percent rating those poor, highlighting infrastructural deficiencies. Laboratory use was limited revealing a gap between theory and practice. ICT integration remained minimal, with 20 percent reporting regular use in teaching. The school environment was largely inclusive, with 70.8 percent reporting no discrimination, yet 28.4 percent felt excluded from decision-making. Positive perceptions were noted in safety, teacher-student rapport, peer respect, and cultural sensitivity, though improvements are needed. The findings underscore the necessity of enhancing resource provision, promoting inclusivity, and fostering collaborative governance to advance educational quality and equity in these schools.

Keywords: Science Education, ICT Integration, Marginalized Communities, School Inclusivity, Educational Infrastructure